

Chemical Evolution of R-process Elements in Stars (CERES)

III. Chemical abundances of neutron capture elements from Ba to Eu

L. Lombardo¹, C. J. Hansen¹, F. Rizzuti², G. Cescutti^{2,3,4}, L. I. Mashonkina⁵, P. François^{6,7}, P. Bonifacio⁶, E. Caffau⁶, A. Alencastro Puls¹, R. Fernandes de Melo¹, A. J. Gallagher⁸, Á. Skúladóttir⁹, A. J. Koch-Hansen¹⁰, and L. Sbordone¹¹

¹ Goethe University Frankfurt, Institute for Applied Physics (IAP), Max-von-Laue-Str. 12, 60438, Frankfurt am Main
e-mail: Lombardo@iap.uni-frankfurt.de

² Dipartimento di Fisica, Sezione di Astronomia, Università di Trieste, Via G. B. Tiepolo 11, 34143 Trieste, Italy

³ INAF, Osservatorio Astronomico di Trieste, Via Tiepolo 11, 34143 Trieste, Italy

⁴ INFN, Sezione di Trieste, Via A. Valerio 2, 34127 Trieste, Italy

⁵ Institute of Astronomy, Russian Academy of Sciences, Pyatnitskaya 48, 119017, Moscow, Russia

⁶ GEPI, Observatoire de Paris, Université PSL, CNRS, 5 place Jules Janssen, 92195 Meudon, France

⁷ UPJV, Université de Picardie Jules Verne, Pôle Scientifique, 33 rue St Leu, 80039 Amiens, France

⁸ Leibniz-Institut für Astrophysik Potsdam, An der Sternwarte 16, 14482 Potsdam, Germany

⁹ Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia, Università degli Studi di Firenze, Via G. Sansone 1, I-50019 Sesto Fiorentino, Italy

¹⁰ Zentrum für Astronomie der Universität Heidelberg, Astronomisches Rechen-Institut, Mönchhofstr. 12, 69120 Heidelberg, Germany

¹¹ ESO-European Southern Observatory, Alonso de Cordova 3107, Vitacura, Santiago, Chile

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ABSTRACT

Context. The chemical abundances of elements such as barium and the lanthanides are essential to understand the nucleosynthesis of heavy elements in the early Universe as well as the contribution of different neutron capture processes (e.g. slow versus rapid) at different epochs.

Aims. The Chemical Evolution of R-process Elements in Stars (CERES) project aims to provide a homogeneous analysis of a sample of metal-poor stars ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$) to improve our understanding of the nucleosynthesis of neutron capture elements, in particular the r -process elements, in the early Galaxy.

Methods. Our data consist of a sample of high resolution and high signal-to-noise ratio UVES spectra. The chemical abundances were derived through spectrum synthesis, using the same model atmospheres and stellar parameters as derived in the first paper of the CERES series.

Results. We measured chemical abundances or upper limits of seven heavy neutron capture elements (Ba, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, and Eu) for a sample of 52 metal-poor giant stars. We estimated through the mean shift clustering algorithm that at $[\text{Ba}/\text{H}] = -2.4$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.4$ a variation in the trend of $[\text{X}/\text{Ba}]$, with $\text{X} = \text{La}, \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Eu}$, versus $[\text{Ba}/\text{H}]$ occurs. This result suggests that, for $[\text{Ba}/\text{H}] < -2.4$, Ba nucleosynthesis in the Milky Way halo is primarily due to the r -process, while for $[\text{Ba}/\text{H}] > -2.4$ the effect of the s -process contribution begins to be visible. In our sample, stars with $[\text{Ba}/\text{Eu}]$ compatible with Solar system pure r -process value (hereafter, r -pure) do not show any particular trend compared to other stars, suggesting r -pure stars may form in similar environments to stars with less pure r -process enrichments.

Conclusions. Homogeneous investigations of high resolution and signal-to-noise ratio spectra are crucial for studying the heavy elements formation, as they provide abundances that can be used to test nucleosynthesis models as well as Galactic chemical evolution models.

Key words. stars: abundances – stars: Population II – Galaxy: abundances – Galaxy: stellar content – nuclear reactions, nucleosynthesis, abundances

References

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Appendix A: Additional tables

Table A.2. List of atomic data without hyperfine and isotopic structure.

Table A.1. Stellar parameters for our sample stars as derived in Paper I.

Star	T_{eff} K	$\log g$ dex	v_{turb} km s^{-1}	[Fe/H] dex
CES0031–1647	4960	1.83	1.91	–2.49
CES0045–0932	5023	2.29	1.76	–2.95
CES0048–1041	4856	1.68	1.93	–2.48
CES0055–3345	5056	2.45	1.66	–2.36
CES0059–4524	5129	2.72	1.56	–2.39
CES0102–6143	5083	2.37	1.75	–2.86
CES0107–6125	5286	2.97	1.54	–2.59
CES0109–0443	5206	2.74	1.69	–3.23
CES0215–2554	5077	2.00	1.91	–2.73
CES0221–2130	4908	1.84	1.84	–1.99
CES0242–0754	4713	1.36	2.03	–2.90
CES0301+0616	5224	3.01	1.51	–2.93
CES0338–2402	5244	2.78	1.62	–2.81
CES0413+0636	4512	1.10	2.01	–2.24
CES0419–3651	5092	2.29	1.78	–2.81
CES0422–3715	5104	2.46	1.68	–2.45
CES0424–1501	4646	1.74	1.74	–1.79
CES0430–1334	5636	3.07	1.63	–2.09
CES0444–1228	4575	1.40	1.92	–2.54
CES0518–3817	5291	3.06	1.49	–2.49
CES0527–2052	4772	1.81	1.84	–2.75
CES0547–1739	4345	0.90	2.01	–2.05
CES0747–0405	4111	0.54	2.08	–2.25
CES0900–6222	4329	0.94	1.98	–2.11
CES0908–6607	4489	0.90	2.12	–2.62
CES0919–6958	4430	0.70	2.17	–2.46
CES1116–7250	4106	0.48	2.14	–2.74
CES1221–0328	5145	2.76	1.60	–2.96
CES1222+1136	4832	1.72	1.93	–2.91
CES1226+0518	5341	2.84	1.60	–2.38
CES1228+1220	5089	2.04	1.87	–2.32
CES1237+1922	4960	1.86	1.95	–3.19
CES1245–2425	5023	2.35	1.72	–2.85
CES1322–1355	4960	1.81	1.96	–2.93
CES1402+0941	4682	1.35	2.01	–2.79
CES1405–1451	4642	1.58	1.81	–1.87
CES1413–7609	4782	1.72	1.87	–2.52
CES1427–2214	4913	1.99	1.85	–3.05
CES1436–2906	5280	3.15	1.42	–2.15
CES1543+0201	5157	2.77	1.57	–2.65
CES1552+0517	5013	2.30	1.72	–2.60
CES1732+2344	5370	2.82	1.65	–2.57
CES1804+0346	4390	0.80	2.12	–2.48
CES1942–6103	4748	1.53	2.01	–3.34
CES2019–6130	4590	1.13	2.09	–2.97
CES2103–6505	4916	2.05	1.85	–3.58
CES2231–3238	5222	2.67	1.67	–2.77
CES2232–4138	5194	2.76	1.59	–2.58
CES2250–4057	5634	2.51	1.88	–2.14
CES2254–4209	4805	1.98	1.79	–2.88
CES2330–5626	5028	2.31	1.75	–3.10
CES2334–2642	4640	1.42	2.02	–3.48

Notes. [Fe/H] is computed with the Solar abundance from Caffau et al. (2011).

Element	Wavelength ($\text{\AA}$)	χ_{exc}	$\log g_f$
Ba II	5853.668	0.604	–1.01
Ba II	6141.713	0.703	–0.08
Ba II	6496.897	0.604	–0.38
La II	3949.100	0.403	0.49
La II	4086.710	0.000	–0.07
La II	4123.220	0.321	0.13
La II	4920.980	0.126	–0.58
Ce II	3577.456	0.470	0.14
Ce II	3999.237	0.295	0.06
Ce II	4073.474	0.477	0.21
Ce II	4083.222	0.700	0.27
Ce II	4118.143	0.696	0.13
Ce II	4120.827	0.320	–0.37
Ce II	4137.645	0.516	0.40
Ce II	4165.599	0.909	0.52
Ce II	5274.229	1.044	0.13
Pr II	4408.810	0.000	0.05
Pr II	5259.731	0.633	0.12
Pr II	5322.770	0.482	–0.12
Nd II	3784.240	0.380	0.15
Nd II	3826.410	0.064	–0.41
Nd II	4021.330	0.320	–0.10
Nd II	4446.380	0.204	–0.35
Nd II	4959.120	0.064	–0.80
Nd II	5255.510	0.204	–0.67
Nd II	5293.160	0.822	0.10
Nd II	5319.810	0.550	–0.14
Sm II	4434.320	0.378	–0.07
Sm II	4704.400	0.000	–0.86
Eu II	3819.670	0.000	0.51
Eu II	4129.720	0.000	0.22
Eu II	6645.060	1.379	0.12

Table A.3. Hyperfine and isotopic structure for Ba II lines ($Z=56$).

Wavelength Å	Isotope	χ_{exc}	$\log gf$
5853.686	137	0.604	-2.066
5853.687	135	0.604	-2.066
5853.687	137	0.604	-2.009
5853.688	135	0.604	-2.009
5853.689	135	0.604	-2.215
5853.689	137	0.604	-2.215
5853.690	134	0.604	-1.010
5853.690	135	0.604	-2.620
5853.690	135	0.604	-1.914
5853.690	135	0.604	-1.466
5853.690	136	0.604	-1.010
5853.690	137	0.604	-2.620
5853.690	137	0.604	-1.914
5853.690	137	0.604	-1.466
5853.690	138	0.604	-1.010
5853.691	135	0.604	-2.215
5853.692	137	0.604	-2.215
5853.693	135	0.604	-2.009
5853.693	137	0.604	-2.009
5853.694	135	0.604	-2.066
5853.694	137	0.604	-2.066
6141.725	135	0.704	-2.456
6141.725	137	0.704	-2.456
6141.727	135	0.704	-1.311
6141.727	137	0.704	-1.311
6141.728	135	0.704	-2.284
6141.728	137	0.704	-2.284
6141.729	135	0.704	-1.214
6141.729	135	0.704	-0.503
6141.729	137	0.704	-1.214
6141.729	137	0.704	-0.503
6141.730	134	0.704	-0.077
6141.730	136	0.704	-0.077
6141.730	138	0.704	-0.077
6141.731	135	0.704	-1.327
6141.731	135	0.704	-0.709
6141.731	137	0.704	-1.327
6141.731	137	0.704	-0.709
6141.732	135	0.704	-1.281
6141.732	135	0.704	-0.959
6141.732	137	0.704	-0.959
6141.733	137	0.704	-1.281
6496.898	137	0.604	-1.886
6496.899	135	0.604	-1.886
6496.901	137	0.604	-1.186
6496.902	135	0.604	-1.186
6496.906	135	0.604	-0.739
6496.906	137	0.604	-0.739
6496.910	134	0.604	-0.380
6496.910	136	0.604	-0.380
6496.910	138	0.604	-0.380
6496.916	135	0.604	-1.583
6496.916	137	0.604	-1.583
6496.917	135	0.604	-1.186
6496.918	137	0.604	-1.186
6496.920	135	0.604	-1.186
6496.922	137	0.604	-1.186

Table A.4. Hyperfine and isotopic structure for La II lines ($Z=57$).

Wavelength Å	Isotope	χ_{exc}	$\log gf$
3949.0377	139	0.403	-1.337
3949.0387	139	0.403	-1.191
3949.0444	139	0.403	-0.995
3949.0460	139	0.403	-1.008
3949.0470	139	0.403	-1.669
3949.0559	139	0.403	-0.761
3949.0582	139	0.403	-0.886
3949.0598	139	0.403	-1.559
3949.0723	139	0.403	-0.576
3949.0752	139	0.403	-0.825
3949.0775	139	0.403	-1.581
3949.0936	139	0.403	-0.420
3949.0972	139	0.403	-0.821
3949.1001	139	0.403	-1.690
3949.1199	139	0.403	-0.284
3949.1241	139	0.403	-0.887
3949.1277	139	0.403	-1.901
3949.1512	139	0.403	-0.163
3949.1561	139	0.403	-1.092
3949.1603	139	0.403	-2.306
4086.6947	139	0.000	-1.266
4086.6986	139	0.000	-1.108
4086.7022	139	0.000	-1.119
4086.7054	139	0.000	-1.292
4086.7070	139	0.000	-0.696
4086.7086	139	0.000	-1.094
4086.7099	139	0.000	-1.790
4086.7109	139	0.000	-3.219
4086.7116	139	0.000	-1.468
4086.7171	139	0.000	-1.292
4086.7186	139	0.000	-1.119
4086.7198	139	0.000	-1.108
4086.7208	139	0.000	-1.266
4123.2021	139	0.321	-0.472
4123.2120	139	0.321	-1.212
4123.2121	139	0.321	-0.643
4123.2201	139	0.321	-2.212
4123.2202	139	0.321	-1.030
4123.2204	139	0.321	-0.850
4123.2267	139	0.321	-1.794
4123.2270	139	0.321	-0.996
4123.2273	139	0.321	-1.121
4123.2319	139	0.321	-1.560
4123.2322	139	0.321	-1.055
4123.2325	139	0.321	-1.539
4123.2357	139	0.321	-1.414
4123.2360	139	0.321	-1.238
4123.2381	139	0.321	-1.317

Table A.5. Hyperfine and isotopic structure for Pr II lines ($Z=59$).

Wavelength Å	Isotope	χ_{exc}	$\log gf$
4408.7323	141	0.000	-0.562
4408.7696	141	0.000	-1.734
4408.7797	141	0.000	-0.655
4408.8019	141	0.000	-3.233
4408.8119	141	0.000	-1.544
4408.8204	141	0.000	-0.754
4408.8392	141	0.000	-2.905
4408.8478	141	0.000	-1.502
4408.8547	141	0.000	-0.859
4408.8701	141	0.000	-2.818
4408.8771	141	0.000	-1.556
4408.8825	141	0.000	-0.968
4408.8945	141	0.000	-2.964
4408.8999	141	0.000	-1.746
4408.9037	141	0.000	-1.077
5259.6145	141	0.633	-3.727
5259.6329	141	0.633	-3.418
5259.6498	141	0.633	-3.356
5259.6653	141	0.633	-3.539
5259.6667	141	0.633	-1.961
5259.6789	141	0.633	-1.763
5259.6897	141	0.633	-1.716
5259.6991	141	0.633	-1.767
5259.7070	141	0.633	-1.965
5259.7251	141	0.633	-0.538
5259.7312	141	0.633	-0.603
5259.7358	141	0.633	-0.669
5259.7390	141	0.633	-0.737
5259.7408	141	0.633	-0.806
5259.7411	141	0.633	-0.874
5322.6702	141	0.482	-3.392
5322.6704	141	0.482	-3.320
5322.6714	141	0.482	-3.710
5322.6718	141	0.482	-3.488
5322.7044	141	0.482	-2.073
5322.7102	141	0.482	-1.878
5322.7173	141	0.482	-1.826
5322.7257	141	0.482	-1.871
5322.7297	141	0.482	-1.164
5322.7354	141	0.482	-2.066
5322.7427	141	0.482	-1.082
5322.7571	141	0.482	-0.998
5322.7727	141	0.482	-0.915
5322.7897	141	0.482	-0.836
5322.8079	141	0.482	-0.760

Table A.6. Hyperfine and isotopic structure for Nd II lines ($Z=60$).

Wavelength Å	Isotope	χ_{exc}	$\log gf$
4446.3635	143	0.204	-3.228
4446.3647	143	0.204	-3.021
4446.3648	143	0.204	-2.228
4446.3657	143	0.204	-1.776
4446.3664	143	0.204	-2.017
4446.3665	143	0.204	-2.993
4446.3677	143	0.204	-1.658
4446.3686	143	0.204	-1.921
4446.3690	143	0.204	-3.073
4446.3703	143	0.204	-1.540
4446.3714	143	0.204	-1.885
4446.3722	143	0.204	-3.265
4446.3735	143	0.204	-1.428
4446.3749	143	0.204	-1.901
4446.3750	145	0.204	-3.228
4446.3758	145	0.204	-2.228
4446.3758	145	0.204	-3.021
4446.3763	143	0.204	-3.654
4446.3764	145	0.204	-1.776
4446.3769	145	0.204	-2.017
4446.3769	145	0.204	-2.993
4446.3773	143	0.204	-1.324
4446.3774	142	0.204	-0.350
4446.3777	145	0.204	-1.658
4446.3782	145	0.204	-1.921
4446.3785	145	0.204	-3.073
4446.3791	143	0.204	-1.983
4446.3793	145	0.204	-1.540
4446.3800	145	0.204	-1.885
4446.3805	145	0.204	-3.265
4446.3813	145	0.204	-1.428
4446.3817	143	0.204	-1.228
4446.3821	145	0.204	-1.901
4446.3829	144	0.204	-0.350
4446.3830	145	0.204	-3.654
4446.3836	145	0.204	-1.324
4446.3840	143	0.204	-2.201
4446.3847	145	0.204	-1.983
4446.3864	145	0.204	-1.228
4446.3869	143	0.204	-1.138
4446.3878	145	0.204	-2.201
4446.3882	146	0.204	-0.350
4446.3896	145	0.204	-1.138
4446.3928	143	0.204	-1.054
4446.3932	145	0.204	-1.054
4446.3937	148	0.204	-0.350
4446.4000	150	0.204	-0.350

Table A.7. Hyperfine and isotopic structure for Eu II lines ($Z=63$).

Wavelength ($\text{\AA}$)	Isotope	χ_{exc}	$\log gf$
3819.5576	151	0.000	-0.620
3819.5746	151	0.000	-0.511
3819.5763	151	0.000	-1.289
3819.5983	151	0.000	-0.402
3819.6008	151	0.000	-1.099
3819.6026	151	0.000	-2.507
3819.6243	153	0.000	-0.620
3819.6285	151	0.000	-0.297
3819.6320	151	0.000	-1.045
3819.6326	153	0.000	-1.290
3819.6333	153	0.000	-0.511
3819.6345	151	0.000	-2.363
3819.6443	153	0.000	-2.509
3819.6450	153	0.000	-1.099
3819.6452	153	0.000	-0.402
3819.6593	153	0.000	-0.297
3819.6600	153	0.000	-2.363
3819.6602	153	0.000	-1.045
3819.6649	151	0.000	-0.198
3819.6697	151	0.000	-1.087
3819.6732	151	0.000	-2.445
3819.6752	153	0.000	-0.198
3819.6777	153	0.000	-1.087
3819.6785	153	0.000	-2.444
3819.6919	153	0.000	-0.106
3819.6968	153	0.000	-1.277
3819.6993	153	0.000	-2.776
3819.7074	151	0.000	-0.105
3819.7137	151	0.000	-1.277
3819.7185	151	0.000	-2.771
4129.5966	151	0.000	-1.512
4129.6001	151	0.000	-1.035
4129.6137	151	0.000	-1.316
4129.6185	151	0.000	-0.977
4129.6220	151	0.000	-1.512
4129.6387	151	0.000	-1.257
4129.6444	151	0.000	-0.847
4129.6492	151	0.000	-1.316
4129.6716	151	0.000	-1.294
4129.6774	153	0.000	-1.513
4129.6781	151	0.000	-0.696
4129.6801	153	0.000	-1.035
4129.6838	151	0.000	-1.257
4129.6838	153	0.000	-1.316
4129.6871	153	0.000	-0.977
4129.6898	153	0.000	-1.513
4129.6941	153	0.000	-1.257
4129.6974	153	0.000	-0.847
4129.7007	153	0.000	-1.316
4129.7091	153	0.000	-1.294
4129.7117	153	0.000	-0.697
4129.7130	151	0.000	-1.480
4129.7150	153	0.000	-1.257
4129.7198	151	0.000	-0.545
4129.7263	151	0.000	-1.294
4129.7295	153	0.000	-1.480
4129.7305	153	0.000	-0.545
4129.7331	153	0.000	-1.294
4129.7548	153	0.000	-0.401
4129.7558	153	0.000	-1.480

Table A.7. continued.

Wavelength (Å)	Isotope	χ_{exc}	$\log gf$
4129.7700	151	0.000	-0.401
4129.7769	151	0.000	-1.480
6645.0717	151	1.379	-0.517
6645.0727	153	1.379	-1.823
6645.0744	153	1.379	-0.517
6645.0749	153	1.379	-3.452
6645.0785	151	1.379	-1.823
6645.0859	151	1.379	-3.480
6645.0876	153	1.379	-0.593
6645.0898	153	1.379	-1.628
6645.0945	153	1.379	-3.151
6645.0974	153	1.379	-0.672
6645.0975	151	1.379	-0.593
6645.1021	153	1.379	-1.583
6645.1047	153	1.379	-0.755
6645.1050	151	1.379	-1.628
6645.1081	153	1.379	-3.079
6645.1101	153	1.379	-0.839
6645.1107	153	1.379	-1.635
6645.1125	151	1.379	-3.144
6645.1144	153	1.379	-0.921
6645.1164	153	1.379	-1.830
6645.1170	153	1.379	-3.236
6645.1194	151	1.379	-0.672
6645.1270	151	1.379	-1.583
6645.1341	151	1.379	-3.082
6645.1376	151	1.379	-0.754
6645.1448	151	1.379	-1.635
6645.1513	151	1.379	-3.237
6645.1525	151	1.379	-0.839
6645.1590	151	1.379	-1.829
6645.1643	151	1.379	-0.921

Appendix C: Additional plots

Fig. C.1. $[Ba/H]$, $[La/H]$, $[Ce/H]$, $[Pr/H]$, $[Nd/H]$, $[Sm/H]$, $[Eu/H]$ abundances as a function of $[C/N]$ for our sample of stars. The open/filled star symbols represent mixed/unmixed stars according to the classification in Paper II (mixed: $[N/Fe]>0.5$ and $[C/N]<-0.6$, unmixed: $[N/Fe]<0.5$ and $[C/N]>-0.6$). The filled circles represent stars that have values outside the ranges defined for mixed and unmixed stars.

Fig. C.2. [Ce/Ba] and [Pr/Ba] abundance ratios as a function of [Ba/H]. The black arrows represent upper limits of abundance ratios. A representative error bar is shown in the upper-right corner of each panel.

Fig. C.3. [Ce/La], [Pr/La], [Nd/La], [Sm/La] abundance ratios as a function of [La/H]. Coloured symbols as in Fig. C.2.

Fig. C.4. $[\text{Pr}/\text{Ce}]$, $[\text{Nd}/\text{Ce}]$, $[\text{Sm}/\text{Ce}]$ abundance ratios as a function of $[\text{Ce}/\text{H}]$. Coloured symbols as in Fig. C.2.

Fig. C.5. $[\text{Pr}/\text{Nd}]$ and $[\text{Sm}/\text{Nd}]$ abundance ratios as a function of $[\text{Nd}/\text{H}]$, and $[\text{Pr}/\text{Sm}]$ abundance ratio as a function of $[\text{Sm}/\text{H}]$. Coloured symbols as in Fig. C.2.

Fig. C.6. [La/Eu], [Ce/Eu], [Pr/Eu], [Nd/Eu] and [Sm/Eu] abundance ratios as a function of [Eu/H]. Coloured symbols as in Fig. C.2.

Fig. C.7. $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}]$ abundance ratios as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for our sample of stars (red stars) and MINCE data (François et al. 2024, cyan squares) compared to the GCE models of Cescutti & Chiappini (2014) (left), Cescutti et al. (2015) (centre), and Rizzuti et al. (2021) (right, see text for more details).